

Lexical-Semantic And Functional Analysis Of Translations From The Arabic Press

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Abstract. This article focuses on aspects considered crucial in editing translations from the Arabic press. Materials from the "Dunyo" news agency were analyzed, examining the role and responsibilities of the editor. For instance, the study investigates aspects that require attention in translating headline ensembles or quotations, as well as in editing facts and realia.

Keywords: translated text, editing, editor, headline ensemble, quotations, Arabic press, adequacy.

Introduction. News and articles published in the Arab press directly related to our country are being translated by the "Dunyo" news agency and posted on its internet and social media pages. This article analyzes the editing of materials translated from the Arabic press into Uzbek, the editor's role in working with translated text, particularly the headline ensemble and the editor's assessment of quotation translations based on the materials of "Dunyo" news agency.

First, it should be noted that the editing of translations in the Uzbek language, its nature, theoretical foundations, and methodology have been practically unstudied. However, the Uzbek school of translation theory and translation studies has long been established. Therefore, when discussing the editing of translated texts, it is advisable to rely on the conclusions, scientific views, and translation products of Uzbek translation school representatives regarding the translation process. After all, the first editor of a translated text is primarily the translator: they work on the translation, make corrections, and search for the most suitable Uzbek equivalent for foreign words or phrases. Naturally, this process incorporates certain elements of editing.

Literature analysis and methodology. The material processed by the translator is further refined by the editor: if the editor knows the target language, it's even better. They notice and correct nuances that the translator might have missed. Even if they don't know the source language, they work according to the logical principles of editing. Therefore, in our opinion, when developing the theoretical foundations of translation text editing, it is appropriate to consider aspects of the translator's editing, editing by an editor who knows the target language, and editing by an editor who does not know the source language. Based on these considerations, let's analyze the headline ensemble and the editing of quotations from the Arabic press published on the "Dunyo" news agency website.

Oman's popular newspaper "Asdaa Oman" published an article about the signing of a law in Uzbekistan on the use of digital evidence to combat cybercrime. The following aspects were noted when comparing the translation with the original text.

There are some errors in the translation related to word usage. For example, the phrase "the law was adopted" was used in the translation. However, the Arabic report states that the law was "signed": "وَقَعَ الرَّئِيسُ الْأُوْزْبِكِيَّ" (translated: "President Shavkat Mirziyoyev signed a historic law"). While the phrase "the law was adopted" may be correct in Uzbek, in this case it implies that the law was adopted by legislative bodies. The Arabic translation uses the term "signing" to emphasize the role of the Head of State in enacting this law. The Uzbek text should have clearly differentiated between the signing and adoption of the law. In the Arabic text, "signing" clearly indicates the law's entry into legal force. In the Arabic text, "signing" clearly indicates the entry of the law into legal force.

Additionally, the phrase "digital evidence" is expressed in Arabic as "الأدلة الرقمية". This phrase was used correctly in the translation, but in some instances, this term should have been explained in more detail within the legal context. In the Arabic text, "الأدلة الرقمية" is used in a broad sense, referring not only to legal evidence but to all information in electronic form. In the translation, the term could be more precise in a legal context, for example, by using "digital legal evidence."

Results. Another issue overlooked by the editor in this translation relates to the use of the phrases "review" and "discuss." The phrase "After several reviews" in the translation corresponds to the Arabic "تم استعراض"

القانون عدة مرات ("The law was reviewed several times"). The meaning would be clearer if words like "discuss" or "coordinate" were used in the translated text, rather than "review" for the Arabic word "استعراض". There is a subtle difference between "review" and "discuss" in terms of their connotations.

Furthermore, the Uzbek text uses the phrase "development," which can lead to ambiguity in some cases. In the Arabic text, the word "تطوير" is used to mean "development of the law" or "improvement of the law." To increase accuracy in the Uzbek text, it could have used "draft law": "بدأ تطوير القانون في عام 2022" ("The improvement of the draft law began in 2022").

Another phrase in the article requiring editorial attention was overlooked. The Arabic phrase "التحقق من الأصل" (verifying the original and confirming the accuracy of the copy) is expressed in Uzbek as "collection, presentation, consolidation, inspection of digital evidence." Replacing "consolidation" in the translation with a more precise word such as "verification" or "authentication" would improve the meaning. The Arabic text uses the word for "confirmation" (التأكد), which is more accurate than "consolidation," a term rarely used in this context in Uzbek.

Another significant edit in this translated text relates to terms for specific state structures. The translated text refers to the "Oliy Majlis" and its "Legislative Chamber," which indicates a specific state structure. In the Arabic text, the word "مجلس الشيوخ" is used, which is the exact equivalent of "Senate." For greater accuracy, the Uzbek text should have used "Senate" instead.

There are some errors in word usage in the translation. Some words should have been more precise in the legal context, and the meaning of certain words in the translation needs further clarification.

Discussion. We will also provide comments on the editing of another article translation by Omon published in this media. The article title "Uzbekistan exports its products to 115 countries" has been translated accurately and informatively. The title clearly expresses the important figure (115 countries) and the main activity (exporting). In Arabic, the title is "أوزبكستان تصدر منتجاتها إلى 115 دولة حول العالم," where the phrase "حول العالم" ("around the world") is not reflected in the translation, and its addition would provide extra meaning.

It is necessary to address the translation of certain words and phrases in this translation:

- The word "local enterprises" in the translation is expressed as "الشركات المحلية" in the original language, so using the word "companies" instead of "enterprises" would be more accurate.
- The phrase "during January-October of this year" in the translation is not correctly translated from Arabic: the expression "من يناير إلى أكتوبر من هذا العام" does not correspond to the Uzbek language, as the Arabic sentence refers to a monthly interval, while the Uzbek version gives an impression of the whole year.
- The expression "national system" used in the translation is "النظام الوطني" in the Arabic article, where the term "national" is more often used in the sense of "state" or "country." The Arabic translation of "creating a favorable regulatory environment" is "خلق بيئة تنظيمية مواتية," which is correct, but the word "favorable" is used in Arabic as "مواتية" (corresponding); there could be other synonyms for the Uzbek "qulay" (for example, "sincere" or "economical").
- "Entered world markets" - This expression may be ambiguous in the Uzbek language, as the word "entered" means to go somewhere or enter. However, in the Arabic text, the phrase "دخلت الأسواق" (entering the market) is more precise, as it reflects the activity, that is, the process of exporting.
- "Data management system" - The Arabic text clearly expresses "نظام دعم الصادرات الوطني" (national export support system). In the Uzbek language, the meaning of the word "system" is broader, and it is unclear which system is being referred to. It would be more accurate to use "national export support system."

Conclusion. While both translations are mostly correct and accurate, there are differences between some words and phrases. It is necessary to correct and adapt inaccurate or imprecise parts of the translation. There are some ambiguities in the use of words in Uzbek and Arabic texts, but they do not alter the main meaning. Nevertheless, the purpose of the materials in both languages is the same: to increase the export potential of Uzbekistan and connect it with international markets. Although there are some minor ambiguities and semantic differences in the translation, they generally do not harm the overall content of the information provided to the reader.

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